

MEDICAL MARIJUANA PHARMACOLOGY

By Edwin Amuga

The use of medical marijuana is a controversial subject among doctors, scientists, policymakers, and the public stirring strong emotions regarding its safety, legality, decriminalization, effectiveness, and conditions for use, addiction, teenage safety, and its medical potentials. Marijuana also referred to as cannabis, has been used worldwide for a gamut of health conditions for the last 3500 years (Hill, 2015). The recent decades in the medical research fields have been marked by the use of individual components of marijuana and other similar substances for health purposes. The United States Food and Administration is yet to approve the marijuana plant used in the

treatment of health problems. An increasing number of states and the District of Columbia, however, are allowing the use of the plant for specific health purposes and research. In this regard, there is widespread uncertainty on the therapeutic benefits of marijuana and if they outweigh its health risks.

Three cannabinoids have been approved by the FDA namely, Epidiolex, synthetic cannabinoids nabilone, and dronabinol. Epidiolex, derived from marijuana, was approved for use in oral solutions for the treatment of seizures associated with two rare epilepsy forms. Synthetic cannabinoids dronabinol and nabilone were approved for use in the treatment of nausea and vomiting associated with cancer chemotherapy. People who have already taken other medicines to treat these symptoms without good results can use these drugs. Additionally, Dronabinol was approved for the treatment of appetite and weight loss in HIV patients. It contains synthetic delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol which is a component of marijuana while nabilone contains a synthetic substance with a similar chemical structure as delta-8-tetrahydrocannabinol. The U.S Food and Drug Administration approved a dronabinol liquid called Syndros. The agency maintains that selling products containing THC or CBD as dietary supplements is not illegal just like selling foods containing added THC or CBD in interstate commerce.

A report by the National Academies of Science, Engineering, and Medicine published in January 2017 recommends doing research to develop a comprehensive understanding of marijuana health effects

and also recommends regulation change which are barriers making it difficult to research on the health effects of marijuana. The medical use of cannabis has not been rigorously tested due to production restrictions and other governmental regulations. There is limited evidence that supports the argument that marijuana reduces nausea and vomiting in HIV/AIDS patients and reduces muscle spasms and chronic pain.

The use of the drug in the short term increases the significant and minor risk for adverse effects such as feeling tired, vomiting, dizziness, and hallucinations. Long-term use of the drug can result in memory and cognitive problems, addiction risk, schizophrenia in younger people, and accidental intake by children. Many cultures over many centuries have been using marijuana medicinally (Jensen, Chen, Furnish & Wallace, 2015). Many organizations are requesting that cannabis is expunged from the Schedule 1 controlled substances and attendant regulatory and scientific review despite opposition from other organizations such as the American Academy of Pediatrics. Medical cannabis is administered through a number of methods such as lozenges, dermal patches, capsules, tinctures, dermal or oral sprays, vaporizing, cannabis edibles, or smoking dried buds. A number of countries are allowing the use of marijuana in medicine and medical research including Canada, Australia, Chile, Germany, Greece, Israel, the Netherlands, Poland, Peru, Colombia, Uruguay, and Portugal. Thirty-three states in the United States have legalized the use of medicinal cannabis.

Pharmacology of cannabis

Cannabis as a genus has two species that produce necessary psychoactive cannabinoid amounts, that is, *cannabis sativa* and *cannabis indica*, which have been listed in the Schedule 1 list of medicinal plants. The third species *Cannabis ruderalis* has few psychogenic properties. Marijuana has more than 460 compounds, 80 of which interact with cannabis receptors of the brain. The brain cannabis receptors CB1 and CB2 are primary receptors responsible for a range of effects of cannabinoids. These receptors belong to a G protein-coupled receptor group. The brain has high levels of CB1 which are believed to be responsible for psychoactive effects. The body peripherally contains CB2 receptors which are believed to modulate inflammation and pain.

The absorption of cannabinoids depends on the administration route. Vaporized, smoked, and inhaled THC has a bioavailability range from 10 to 35% (D'Souza & Ranganathan, 2015). Orally administered cannabinoids have a low bioavailability rate of 6% as variability in absorption is dependent on the mode administration and the time used to peak plasma levels which range from 2 to 6 hours when compared with vaporized or smoked THC. To improve the low bioavailability of oral preparations, alternative routes are under study such as sublingual and rectal routes to maximize bioavailability and reduce the first-pass metabolism.

Pain control is the most common use of medical marijuana in the United States. Although marijuana is not strong enough to be used to contain severe pain such as in post-surgical pain and broken bone, it is effective in the management of chronic pain plaguing many Americans especially when they are aging. Medical marijuana is also clearly safer than opiates as the case of overdose is reduced and it is less addictive and it can replace NSAIDs such as Aleve or Advil in the case of people with kidney problems or ulcers or GERD who can take them.

Marijuana also eases [pain of multiple sclerosis and general nerve pain. The few other options available in this area are highly sedating such as Lyrica, Neurontin, or opiates. Patients that have used marijuana in the management of these kinds of pain report that it allows them to resume their previous activities devoid of disengagement feelings. Marijuana is also an effective muscle relaxant, and it can lessen tremors in Parkinson's disease. It is also reportedly successful in fibromyalgia, endometriosis, interstitial cystitis, and other chronic pain conditions.

Marijuana is also useful in the management of nausea and weightlessness and is successful in the treatment of glaucoma. Cannabis is also under research for its use in the management of Post-Traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in veterans returning from combat zones. Many therapists working with veterans and their clients have reported drastic improvement and advocate for more studies and loosening of governmental restrictions on the study of marijuana in this regard. Medical marijuana is also reportedly helpful in managing

suffering, pain, and wasting syndrome associated with HIV, irritable bowel syndrome, and Crohn's disease (Bradford & Bradford, 2016). There is a long list of benefits that come along with the adoption of marijuana in medicine and medical research regarding conditions in which the drug is helpful in providing relief. Just like in the case of all other remedies, the claim of the effectiveness of cannabis should be evaluated carefully and treated with caution. It is vital that restrictions on the use of marijuana in medical research be obliterated to give way for the development of marijuana-based medicines that are potentially useful in the management of pain and many diseases and conditions as suggested by history and research.

Structural barriers to accessing medical marijuana in the United States

The United States is experiencing increased use of marijuana as over 7.6 million people in the country use it daily with 30% of the use of marijuana being in disease-related symptom treatment. The medicinal effects of cannabis are under the medical marijuana laws scope regulating medicinal purposes dispensation. Medicinal marijuana laws vary across the United States dictating the access, prescription, dispensation, and permissible therapeutic marijuana use patterns. There are other factors, part form the medicinal marijuana laws that affect the access of medicinal marijuana in the united states and even across the world such as income, race/ethnic background, stigma, and physician characteristics which are merging mechanisms fostering disparity incipient area.

White Americans predominantly use medical marijuana in comparison with Latinos, Asians, and foreign-born individuals. The rationale behind the use of medical marijuana among white Americans remains unclear. Socioeconomic backgrounds are also an impeding factor in accessing and using medical marijuana as a higher number of employed individuals, insurance holders and high-income earners use the medicines in comparison with the poor. Marijuana possession Stigma is also another factor that deters individuals from considering medicinal marijuana. This also prevents qualifying patients from discussing medicinal marijuana with their doctors. Physician attitudes and characteristics are also other predictors in the initiation and continued use of medical marijuana as they follow strict restrictions in their states. due to these factors in addition to medical marijuana laws, many patients with conditions that qualify lack access to medical marijuana.

References

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